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Mechanical characterisation of sandwich structures: a case study comparing common and fire-resistant ACM panels

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Abstract: Aluminium Composite Material (ACM) is a lightweight and strength sandwich structure composed of a homogeneous polymer core and aluminium skins. ACM is a commercially worldwide material primarily for construction applications in two categories: (I) ACM PE consists of low-density polyethylene core, and (II) ACM FR is made of low-density polyethylene core combined with magnesium hydroxide particles targeting fire-resistant requirements. This work is a case study to statistically compare the mechanical properties of ACM PE and ACM FR under three-point bending for decision-making criteria in structural design. Both types of ACM present acceptable mechanical performance, with specific stiffness close to that of aluminium. ACM panels support more than 45 kgf per 90 x 180 mm². While ACM FR has higher absolute strength, ACM PE has higher stiffness and a greater modulus of toughness. ACM PE is superior in terms of specific strength due to its lower structural weight. Their elastic-plastic transitions are similar. ACM FR is not a good choice in terms of mechanical performance unless flame-resistant properties are required.

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1. Introduction

Due to the intrinsic characteristics of lightweight associated with high strength and stiffness, sandwich structures are applied in many industrial sectors, such as aerospace, marine, automotive and civil construction [1]. Specifically dealing with the construction and building materials in the civil sector, there is a great interest in evaluating the mechanical properties of sandwich composites under bending loading [2].

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Aluminium Composite Material (ACM) consists of a particular sandwich structure composed of a homogeneous polymeric core and aluminium skins, manufactured and marketed worldwide mainly for civil construction applications, as the cladding of external facades. ACM panels are usually announced in two categories: (I) ACM PE, which has a simple low-density polyethylene core, and (II) ACM FR, which has a core made of low-density polyethylene reinforced with magnesium hydroxide particles, marketed as fire-resistant ACM.

In [3], the authors presented a novel approach to account for geometric effects on the elastic properties of sandwich structures. The ACM PE and ACM FR were tested under three-point bending to verify the proposed assumptions. Nevertheless, only the flexural modulus of the panels and their phases were evaluated, as well as some geometric parameters – see Table 1.

Table 1. Some data reported in [3].

	ACM PE	ACM FR
Total thickness	4.06 mm	4.14 mm
Global flexural modulus	30.62 GPa	23.62 GPa
Face thickness	0.45 mm	0.30 mm
Face elastic modulus	57.91 GPa	59.85 GPa
Core thickness	3.16 mm	3.54 mm
Core elastic Modulus	0.73 GPa	2.39 GPa

This work proposes a case study to complement the survey and statistical comparison of other mechanical properties of ACM PE and ACM FR under three-point bending: yield force, maximum load, fracture force, modulus of resilience and modulus of toughness. It is intended to evaluate the mechanical performance of both panels for decision-making criteria in the structural design of load-bearing components in construction and building engineering.

2. Methodology

Three-point bending is performed on a Shimadzu AGX universal testing machine, equipped with a 100 kN load cell and a crosshead speed of 3.5 mm/min. Data are collected from 5 (five) specimens for each panel type, and one replica of the sample set is performed, totalling 10 (ten) tests for ACM PE and ACM FR. Specimen dimensions are 90 x 230 mm², and a support span equal to 180 mm is considered. These dimensions are in accordance with ASTM D7250 [4] and are equivalent to Condition A reported in [3, Table 3, p.8]. According to [3], this condition guarantees the pure bending behaviour in ACM FR [3, Table 7 and Fig. 14] and at least 90% of pure bending in ACM PE [3, Table 9 and Fig. 18], comparing the expected flexural modulus with the slope of the straight-line portion of the mean stress-strain curve.

Maximum load and fracture force are obtained from force-displacement data. The yield point is determined by the offset method considering the value of 0.03% for the mean strain after normalising the force-displacement curves for the mean stress-strain according to [3, Eqs. 8 and 9], and the yield force is obtained by locating the yield

point on the force-displacement curves. Modulus of resilience and modulus of toughness are calculated considering the area under mean stress-strain curves up to yield point and fracture point, respectively. All data are statically evaluated in Minitab® [5] to verify normal distribution by the Anderson-Darling test, and the Two-Sample t-Test is used to estimate the difference between properties of ACM PE and ACM FR.

To evaluate the force-displacement data considering specific properties, the bending curves of both ACMs are compared by dividing the force data by the equivalent density of the panels, measured as the ratio of mass to volume in 270 x 360 mm² plates.

3. Results and Discussions

Fig. 1 shows the typical force-displacement curves of both ACM types. At elastic behaviour, the ACM PE consists of a panel of greater stiffness due to greater face thickness (see Table 1 – ACM PE has 50% thicker skins compared to ACM FR). It should be noted that the transition elastic-plastic occurs precociously on ACM PE, since the yield force is greater for ACM FR. Nevertheless, as reported in the Methodology section, the conditions under test guarantee pure bending in ACM FR and 90% of pure bending in ACM PE. The elastic properties of ACM PE are about 10% underestimated by curve interpretation [3]; therefore, the difference between the yield force of ACM PE and ACM FR may not occur in structural applications of pure bending behaviour. This point can also affect the analysis of the modulus of resilience.

Fig. 1. Force-displacement curves of both ACM.

As for the plastic behaviour, it is evident that ACM FR has a higher maximum load supported, although ACM PE absorbs more energy (modulus of toughness) up to the fracture point. These observations can be explained by the higher rigidity of the ACM FR core (see Table 1), which better optimises stress distribution along the skins leading to a higher maximum load even made with thinner skins. The more ductile ACM PE core leads to more deformation from maximum load to fracture point.

Numerical values and descriptive statistics of the means of the properties are shown in Table 2 (yield force, maximum load and fracture force) and Table 3 (modulus of resilience and modulus of toughness). All data are normally distributed ($AD^{P-Value} > 0.05$) and acceptable accuracy with a low coefficient of variation ($CV < 10\%$). The dispersions are greater (greater CV) for panels with a core reinforced with magnesium hydroxide particles (ACM FR), since the distribution of particles in this type of material is random.

Table 2. Force data.

ACM type	Yield Force (N)		Maximum Load (N)		Fracture Force (N)	
	PE	FR	PE	FR	PE	FR
Mean	450.26	493.98	518.29	615.10	473.15	608.22
CV (%)	±1.58	±5.71	±1.20	±3.66	±1.03	±3.86
AD ^{P-Value}	0.656	0.068	0.411	0.763	0.413	0.563
Mean difference	(23.25, 64.21)		(80.34, 113.29)		(117.90, 152.24)	
Increment (PE to FR)	(5.16%, 14.26%) ↑		(15.50%, 21.86%) ↑		(24.92%, 32.18%) ↑	

Table 3. Energy data.

ACM type	Modulus of Resilience (kJ/m ³)		Modulus of Toughness (kJ/m ³)	
	PE	FR	PE	FR
Mean	142.32	185.88	1101.91	855.53
CV (%)	±3.04	±8.94	±2.66	±7.40
AD ^{P-Value}	0.903	0.056	0.906	0.147
Mean difference	(31.47, 55.66)		(191.59, 301.17)	
Increment (PE to FR)	(22.11%, 39.11%) ↑		(17.39%, 27.33%) ↓	

Yield force data range from 5.16% to 14.26% for ACM FR compared to ACM PE, which aligns with the assumption that this difference may not occur in structural applications under pure bending behaviour; since the elastic properties of ACM PE as measured by force-displacement curves are expected to be about 10% underestimated. Maximum load is 15.50% to 21.86% higher in ACM FR. The difference is even more significant (29.92% to 32.18%) for fracture force, as the ACM FR fractures instantly after reaching maximum load. ACME PE

has significant deformation with consequent reduction of the internal forces between the points of maximum load and fracture.

The modulus of resilience varies from 22.11% to 39.11% for ACM FR in relation to ACM PE. However, this comparison may be overshadowed by the fact that the elastic properties of ACM PE are 10% underestimated. The modulus of toughness of ACM FR is 17.39% to 27.33% lower than ACM PE.

The measured equivalent density is 1.30 g/cm³ for ACM PE and 1.63 kg/cm³ for ACM FR. Although ACM PE has 50% thicker skins, the increase in core density by adding magnesium hydroxide particles leads to a greater structural weight in ACM FR (about 25%). Fig. 2 shows the typical force-displacement curves of both types of ACM from a specific point of view, i.e., the curves consider the ratio between the force data and the equivalent density of the panels. It is evident that the mechanical performance of ACM PE is superior in terms of all the specific properties evaluated: yield force, maximum load, fracture force, modulus of resilience and modulus of toughness.

Fig. 2. Specific force-displacement curves of both ACM.

4. Conclusions

ACM PE and ACM FR present acceptable mechanical performance; their equivalent densities are 1.30 and 1.63 kg/cm³, respectively. The specific flexural moduli are 23.55 GPa (ACM PE) and 14.49 GPa (ACM FR). Considering that the elastic modulus and density of aluminium skins is about 60 GPa and 2.7 g/cm³, it is evident that ACM panels are competitive with homogeneous aluminium plates, as the specific elastic modulus of aluminium is about 22.22 GPa. The maximum load of ACM PE is around 450 N (\approx 45 kgf) per 90 x 180 mm², while ACM FR has a strength 15.50% to 21.86% higher than ACM PE. In contrast, ACM PE absorbs more energy to fracture than ACM FR (\approx 1100 kJ compared to \approx 850 kJ per m³). It is worth mentioning that the yield force of both panels is close (with a difference of no more than 10%, which may be overestimated), and the ACM PE achieves more stiffness. ACM PE has a greater structural lightness and greater specific properties. Finally, the ACM FR may not be considered a good choice from a mechanical point of view unless flame-resistant characteristics are required.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

CRediT author statement

R.J. da Silva: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Investigation; Data curation; Formal Analysis; Visualisation; Writing – original draft. **J.C. dos Santos:** Investigation (technical support). **F.B. Batista:** Supervision (MSc advisor). **T.H. Panzera:** Resources (laboratory instrumentation); Supervision (MSc co-advisor); Writing – review.

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